

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

TAXONOMIC STRUCTURE OF ENDEMIC PLANTS SPREADING ONLY IN NAKHCHIVAN AUTONOMOUS REPUBLIC FLORA OF AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

Flora of Nakhchivan AR is rich from species point of view. The reason of this is various ecological medium and relief of the area. From ecological factors – heat, humidity, light, wind and tee, including to climate factor are of great importance in plants development. Soil condition, its mechanical, physical and agrochemical. Structure being edaphic factors, as well as height, slope aspect, inclined feature and surface being orographic factors play important role in plants gravity.

These factors met in the nature of Nakhchivan AR differ from other botanic-geographical regions. From species, point of view mountainous zone of Nakhchivan has great advantages comparing with other botanic-geographical regions of Azerbaijan.

Keywords: endemic, Nakhchivan Territory, ecological, climate factor, status

Introduction

Located in 38⁰31'– 39⁰47' northern latitude and 44⁰46'–46⁰10' eastern longitude of the southwestern part of the hesser Caucasus Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic has severe continental climate. The lowest field in Arazboyu plain (about 600–800 m), the highest peak is Gapijig (3906 m). State border of the Nakhchivan AR is bounded with Islamic Republic of Iran from the South by Araz river, Turkey Republic from the west, Zangazur and Daralayaz ranges and Armenia from the north and east. The main factors forming severe continental climate in the Nakhchivan AR were change of average annual weather temperature: 8–5⁰ C–14–12⁰ C positive, in the coldest months of the year 6–10⁰ C negative minus 30⁰ C frosty days during some years (Babayev S. Y., 1999).

Climate change or stability plays an important role in the formation of endemism center. (Susan Harrison and Reed Noss., 2017). Endemic species have been identified in the study of the flora biodiversity of the Transilvanian plain. (Abramova I.V., 2013, Ishmuratova M.Yu., Tleukenova S.U. et al., 2015, Mihaela Samarghitan, Silvia Oraoian, Corneliu Tanase, 2017). The types of endemic plants in danger of extinction in the Mediterranean Sea, it was noted. (Fenu G., Mattana E.Ş, 2011)

Of the 78% of endemic flowering plants growing in Iran, 42% are bordered by mountainous areas. Thus, at altitudes above 1400 m, the complexity of the microclimate and relief affects high biodiversity and endemism. (Jalil Noroozi, Amir Talebi, Moslem Dosost-mohammedi, Sara Manafzadeh, Zahra Asgarpour and Gerald M., 2019)

In the Brazilian state of Ceppa-gys-Caracas, 38 species of tuberous plants, 31 genera and 7 endemic species of 22 family were identified from 856 seed plants. (Gulietti A.M et al., 2019). According to the size of the distribution conditions in the Carpathians, endemic taxa are divided into 4 main groups: eurychoric (pancarpathic), mesochoric, stenochoric, microchoric. (Jan Kliment, Peter Turis & Monika Janisova, 2018).

Due to the complex climate and high mountainous areas of the study area, the diversity of endemic plants has been formed. (Julio Penas, Francisco J. Perez Garcia & Juan F., 2005; Gulbanu Aueskhanovna, Duman Kulakhmedovich Baizhygitov et al., 2017). Information has been provided on the importance of migration in the protection of endemic plants due to climate change that may occur in the mountainous areas of Tibet. (Yujing Yan and Zhiyao Tang 2019). A number of endangered endemic plants have been identified on Mount Cameroon (Martin Cheek, Isla Causon et al., 2019)

Being surrounded by high mountains in the north and bordered on Araz river in the south, in the territory of the Nakhchivan AR no transitional species are found from neighboring states and specific endemic plant species belonging here are spread.

Materials and methods

For the study of endemic species, plant samples were collected during about 40 expeditions in 2018–2020, starting from the “Arazboyu” plain of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic to the areas covering the middle, high mountains and alpine belt. The collected plant samples were herbariated and put into use. Literary data, flora of Turkey, Iran and Armenia were used to clarify that the species is endemic to the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. Endemic species of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic have been identified using the flora of neighboring countries Turkey, Iran and Armenia. The identified species are divided into systematic groups.

Endemic plants collected during expeditions from the plains of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic to the areas covering the middle and high mountain belt were identified through literature data, identifiers and atlas (Lazkov G.A. and Umralina A.R., 2015; Asgarov A. M., 2016)

The first flowering plants had been known since the Cretaceous period of the Mesozoic era. Flowering plants cover species more than 350 families; they spread throughout the world (the Earth). Being rich in characteristic species, a variety of flowering trees,

shrubs, grass which has grown in the flora of Nakhchivan. Among flowering plants *Liliopsida* or *Monocotyledon* class, constitute more than grasses. 73 species collected in 36 genera of 12 families of the class *Monocotyledons* grow only in the territory of Nakhchivan, one of the 5 largest botanical-geographical regions of Azerbaijan. Another class of flowering plants, *Magnoliopsida* – 467 species belonging to 47 genera, 9 subfamilies, 214 genera of *dicotyledons* are only in the flora of Nakhchivan AR (Asgarov A.M., 2011, 2016; Talibov T.H., Ibrahimov A.S. 2008, 2010; Seyidov M.M., Ibadullayeva J.S., 2014; Aliyeva A. M., 2019). However, yet information was provided on endemic species and their status in the flora of Nakhchivan AR.

Results and discussion

For the first time, information provided on endemic plant species included in the flora of Azerbaijan, growing only in the territory of Nakhchivan AR. The taxonomic composition of endemic plants in the flora of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is as follows:

Liliopsida (Monocotyledones)

Familia: *Poaceae* Barnhart

Genus: *Elytrigia* Desv.

Elytrigia Heidemaniae Tzvel.

Genus: *Bromus* L.

Bromus Tzvelevii S.G.Mussajev

Genus: *Koeleria* Pers.

Koeleria bitzenachica (Tzvel.) Tzvel.

Genus: *Stipa* L.

Stipa Issaevii S.G.Musajev et Sadychov

Stipa Karjaginii S.G.Musajev et Sadychov

Magnoliopsida

Familia: *Ranunculaceae* Juss.

Genus: *Delphinium* L.

Delphinium Lomakinii Kem.-Nath.

Familia: *Chenopodiaceae* Vent.

Genus: *Salsola* L.

Salsola futilis İljin

Familia: *Hypericaceae* Juss.(Guttiferae auct.)

Genus: *Hypericum* L.

Hypericum atropatanum Rzazade

Familia: *Brassicaceae* Burnett

Genus: *Thlaspi* L.

Thlaspi armenum N.Busch

Genus: *Apterigia* Galusko

Apterigia rostrata (N.Busch) Galushko

Genus: *Peltariopsis* N.Busch

Peltariopsis Grossheimii N.Busch

Genus: *Cymatocarpus* O.E.Schultz

Cymatocarpus Grossheimii N.Busch

Genus: *Crambe* L.

Crambe Grossheimii İ.Khalilov

Familia: *Rosaceae* Juss.

Subfamilia: *Maloideae*

Genus: *Crataegus* L.

Crataegus Cinovskisii Kassymova

Familia: *Fabaceae* Lindl.

Subfamilia: *Papilionoideae* or *Faboideae*

Genus: *Astragalus* L.

Astragalus badamliensis Chalilov

Astragalus conspicuus Boriss.(*A.aduncus* Willd.)

Astragalus karakuschensis Gontsch

Genus: *Lathyrus* L.(*Orobus* L.)

Lathyrus atropatanus (Grossh.) Sirj. (*Orobus atropatanus* Grossh.)

Genus: *Trifolium* L. s.str.

Trifolium Biebersteinii Chalilov

Familia: *Rubiaceae* Juss.

Genus: *Galium* L.

Galium achurense Grossh.

Galium atropatanum Grossh.

Galium bullatum Lipsky

Familia: *Scrophulariaceae* Juss.

Genus: *Verbascum* L.(*Celsia* L.)

Verbascum erivanicum E. Wulf.

Genus: *Scrophularia* L.

Scrophularia nachitscvanica Grossh.

Familia: *Lamiaceae* Lindl.

Subfamilia: *Scutellarioideae*

Genus: *Scutellaria* L.

Scutellaria darriensis Grossh.

Scutellaria Karjaginii Grossh.

Scutellaria rhomboidalis Grossh.

Subfamilia: *Lamioideae*

Genus: *Marrubium* L.

Marrubium nanum Knorr.

Genus: *Nepeta* L.

Nepeta noraschenica Grossh.

Genus: *Stachys* L.

Stachys Fominii Sosn.

Genus: *Salvia* L. (*Schraderia* Medik.)

Salvia suffruticosa Montbr. et. Auch. ex Benth. (*S.Alexandri* Pobed.)

Familia: *Asteraceae* Dumort - Asterçiçəklilər or *Compositae* Giseke

Genus: *Carduus* L.

Carduus atropatanucus Sosn. ex Grossh. (*C.onopordioides* Fisch. et Bieb.)

Genus: *Centaurea* L.

Centaurea araxina Gabr.

Genus: *Crepis* L.

Crepis karakuschensis Gzer.

5 species to 4 genera belonging to the class of monocotyledons (all of them belong to the family *Poaceae* Barnhart), 10 genera belonging to the class of *Dicotyledons*, 29 endemic species belonging to 23 genera spread in only Nakhchivan's flora, Azerbaijan. Among the endemic plants, *Lamiaceae* Lindl, a family of *Dicotyledons*, is dominated by 5 genera and 7 species.

Among the endemic plants spread only in Nakhchivan's flora, there are species included in the "Red Book" of Azerbaijan and the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. Information on these species has given in the following table:

**Rare and endangered endemic species included in the “Red Book”
of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic and Republic of Azerbaijan**

№	Latin names of plants	Its status (“Red Book” of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic)	Its status (“Red Book” of Azerbaijan Republic)
<i>Liliopsida (Monocotyledones)</i>			
1.	<i>Stipa Issaevii</i> S.G.Musajev et Sadychov	CR B1ac(i)	
2.	<i>Stipa Karjagini</i> S.G.Musajev et Sadychov	VU Ac; B1b(ii,iii)c (ii,iii)	
<i>Magnoliopsida</i>			
1.	<i>Astragalus badamliensis</i> Chalilov	CR B1ac(ii,iv); C2a(i)	
2.	<i>Astragalus badamliensis</i> Chalilov		CR A2c+3c; B1ac(i)+2ab(i,ii,iii)
3.	<i>Hypericum atropatanum</i> Rzazade		VU D2
4.	<i>Salsola futilis</i> İljin		VU D2
5.	<i>Marribium nanum</i> Knorr.		NT

The analysis of the table shows that the Red Book of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic includes both monocotyledonous and dicotyledonous species of endemic plants, and the Red Book of the Republic of Azerbaijan includes only species belonging to the dicotyledonous class.

Discussion

Only in the flora of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic of Azerbaijan there are 5 endemic species belonging to 4 genera of the Poaceae Barnhart family of the monocotyledonous class, 10 genera belonging to the dicotyledonous class, 29 endemic species belonging to 23 genera of 4 subfamilies. Among the endemic plants, *Lamiaceae* Lindl family, belonging to the class of dicotyledons, is dominated by 5 genera and 7 species. Among the endemic plants, the "Red Book" of the Nakhchivan AR includes representatives of both monocotyledons and dicotyledons, and the "Red Book" of the Republic of Azerbaijan includes only species belonging to the class of dicotyledons.

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